

Assessing Difficulties of Translating Opaque Idioms from English into Arabic: A Case Study

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Abstract

The translation of idiomatic expressions from English into Arabic is considered a difficult task for translators. This difficulty may reveal that this translation has a serious misunderstanding and mistranslation of the source text. This study aims to determine the major challenges that master students in the translation department encounter when translating idioms and identify the methods and strategies for translating such expressions. The study hypothesizes that the commonest challenge that translators encounter when rendering idiomatic expressions into Arabic is cultural differences. The commonest strategies are used by students when rendering idiomatic expressions into Arabic, which include omission, paraphrasing, different form but similar meaning and similar and meaning. The translation of opaque idioms is harder than the transparent ones. Theoretically, the study presents a literature review on translation methods of translation and the relation among translation, language and culture, idioms and difficulties in translating idiomatic expressions, and it tackles translation, models and strategies used in translation idiomatic expressions. Finally, it sets forth a brief account previous study. Practically, the data used for analysis comprise twenty-five idiomatic expressions selected from the videos on the you- tube channels (Interactive English). These idioms are given to 10 M.A. students from the department of translation, college of arts university of Tikrit who voluntarily agreed to take part in the test to translate the selected idioms. In this study Moon's (1998) idioms typology is used as a linguistic model to identify the four types of idioms (The transparent, the semi-transparent, the opaque and the semi-opaque idioms) used by the translators. Newmark's (1981) model of translation is also used to distinguish two methods of translations, semantic and communicative methods. The other is provided by baker (1992). The findings of the study showed that master students face many challenges when translating idiomatic expressions including the lack of awareness of the cultural difference between English and Arabic. This study suggests that it is important to find a target language idiom rather than translating such an idiom by paraphrasing. As well as being familiar with the adopted strategies may help student's abilities translate more properly. Finally, the study displays that the type of idiom has a minor impact on understanding its meaning and aiding an appropriate translation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Movies idioms translating is not an easy process. It necessitates a wide experience of the target language and good skill both in using methods and strategies of translation. The goal of this topic tackles the subject that highlights challenges the translators come across in translating English idioms movies from English into Arabic in given movies for 25 idioms. Translating idioms is a more challenging mission for translators because it requires well acquaintance with both languages and the two Languages are more widely different culturally and linguistically.

Arabic is a Semitic language while English is an Endo-European one. They are far culturally different and cross-cultural. To fulfill this work, 25 idioms of many types are chosen randomly from films according to Moons' linguistic model (1998).

2. Idioms

According to Palmer (1976:79) one cannot guess that the particular meaning is expressed by group of words. Idioms contain collocation of a special types for example (kick the bucket, fly off handle and spill the beans), the matter is not the collocation of words. The combination is opaque. The meaning does not equal the individual words, it sometimes near to one word meaning thus (kick the bucket means die. Some idioms like (kick the bucket) have past but others have restrictions, for example spilled the beans, but not spill the bean. We have the idiom (red herrings), but not (redder herring). Some idioms have passive form while others do not. According to Newmark (1988 p:104) an idiom is regarded an extension of the metaphor that is characterized by two double functions the pragmatic function to attract to sense, to care, to startle to pleasure. The second is aesthetic.

In her work, Baker (1992, p. 63) stated that idioms are fixed linguistic patterns that exhibit minimal variation in form. Furthermore, idioms often convey meanings that cannot be inferred from their individual components. She points out that idioms can be distinguished from collocation by meaning transparency and the pattern flexibility.

Carthy (1992 p:55) stated that idioms constitute group of words of more than two words, whose syntactic structure is somewhat fixed and semantically opaque to some extent. This definition combines both opacity of meaning and frozenness of syntax shares with large of terms such as tourneur idioms, phrasal verbs, cultural allusion and metaphor.

Saberian and Fotovatnia (2011 p: 1231) reported that the word idiom covers large types of variant categories of multi-word units which are group of series of more than two words that form units of meaningful and inseparable groups.

Adelnia and Dastjerdi (2011 p: 879) reported that idioms could be regarded as a section daily language use. They define idioms as expressions of language or items of lexis standing for objects, concepts or phenomena of material life especially to specific culture. They are important to any speech sound system to maintain the color of culture and localization of particular sound system speech.

According to Horvathova (2014 p:96) the meaning of idioms is expressions which does not follow the semantic principle of compositionality which depends on the individual words meaning making up the idiom. This is the reason which make literal translation does not always succeed to predict the right meaning of the idiom from their components, hence we translate them communicatively. Juknevcienė (2017 p:7) defines phraseology as “the selection or arrangement of words and phrases in the expression of ideas, manner or style of expression, the particular language, terminology or diction which characterizes a writer, work, subject, language, place, etc.”. Phraseology is used recently by linguists to denote to the field of interdisciplinary studies that comprise a wide scale of unchangeable and semi frozen expressions. Like these constructions work in speech sound system as entire units. They are in increasing way treated by researchers as separated components of lexes.

Fawzi (2018 P:364) stated that for decades idioms were regarded lexemic combinations, he argues that they should be studied from the properties of pragmatics and classifies them as an implicature umbrella as sub-division of conversational implicatures, for they have invisible meaning. For example, if we described an argument as a red herring this would mean it is irrelevant and distracting, it is obvious that the matter is not related to fish nor to the red color.

3. Classifications of idioms

Many bases have been put by many scholars to the taxonomy of idioms they will be shown in detail, some of them are syntactic others are compositional and pragmatic. Another categorization deals with the field of idiom such as food, medicine, sport...etc. This classification will be excluded because it is not a linguistic one. Idioms constitute a crucial part of language for they deviate from the norm of compositionality and have unique restrictions.

Makkai (1972 p: 312-340) classified idioms into two main types

- A. Semitic idioms contain proverbs and similar structure of sentence length.
- B. Lexemic idioms which are constructed from more than one minimal free form can further also subdivided into:
 1. Phrasal verb idioms
These idioms are composed of verb +adverb. Some adverbs are prepositions. Some verbs are transitive others are intransitive. They are known as (phrase verbs) for example:
Please turn on the light. This room is dark. The idiom (turn on) means to start the lamp.
 2. Tourneur idioms
These idioms are consisting of verb phrases. They are composed of at least three words or lexicons plus definite or indefinite articles and have metaphorical meaning. For example,
(To blow a fuse) which means to get very angry.
 3. Irreversible Binomial Idioms
They are idioms which are composed of two lexicons and separated by conjunction.

4. Phrasal Compound Idioms

They are common forms of idioms. They may be as one word.

The meaning is different from its constituent and includes primary nominal. They have many patterns as shown below:

- A. Adjective +noun for example (greenhorn) which means an inexperienced man.
- B. Noun +noun for example (egghead) which means intellectual.
- C. Verb +noun for example (kill-joy) which means spoils the pleasure of others.

5. Incorporated Verb Idioms. They are always hyphenated.

They can also subdivide into

- A. Noun-Verb, for example (Sight –see) which means visiting famous cities in an area.
 - B. Adjective-Noun, for example (black-mail) which means threatening a person to reveal a secret if he does not pay money.
 - C. Noun +Noun for example (boot-leg) which means made and sold illegally way
 - D. Adjective +Verb, for example (white-wash) which means to hide the truth about someone or something.
6. Pseudo-Idioms: for example (Cranberry face) which means to deceive someone.
 7. Simile-Idioms: consist of *as* and a *noun, verb, or an adjective*, for example (sleep as baby), (brown as berry), (chatter like magpie).
 8. Proverb –Idioms: have literal and moral meaning for example (do not count chickens before they were hatched).

Nunberg Taxonomy (1978) quoted in Siberian and Fotovatina (2011p:1231) mentioned three categories:

1. Normally decomposable idioms for example (pop the question) in this type a part of the idiom is used here the word question is used literally.
2. Abnormal decomposable idioms in this type a part of idiom is known metaphorically for example buck in (pass the buck)
3. Semantically non –decomposable idioms the meaning is not compositional for example (chew the fat).

The Compositional categorization of Cacciari and Glucksbergs' taxonomy, includes three types (ibid):

1. Opaque idioms like (kick the bucket).
2. Transparent idioms such as (spill the beans).
3. Quasi-metaphorical idioms: in this type of idiom, the idiomatic meaning is mapped to the literal one.

Yoshika's Taxonomy (2011) included five classes (Ibid):

1. Type (A) Structural and semantically is similar to L1.
2. Type (B) is partially similar to L1.
3. Type (C1) has a similar structure but a variant meaning to L1.
4. Type (C2) is dissimilar semantically and structurally to L1.
5. Type (D) has a similar meaning but a variant structure to L1.

The degree of L1 and L2 structural and semantic similarity is taken as the bases of classification idioms.

According to Fernando (1996) classifications idioms is grouped into:

1. Pure idioms such spill the beans the principle of compositionality does not lead to the meaning.
2. Semi-idiom one part is literal and the other is non –literal like (foot the bill) which means pay the bill.
3. Literal idiom can be understood directly like (on foot).

His classification is based on lexical variation.

While Halliday, (1985) pointed out three types:

1. Ideational idioms like (a watched pot never boils) they are sensory affective and evaluative.
2. Interpersonal idioms are interactional or symbolize the message's nature, for example (let's face it), (come off it), and (good afternoon).
3. Rational idioms that service the coherence and cohesion of the discourse like (on the contrary), (as distinct from), and (to cap it all).

According to Hockett (1958), there are six classes:

1. Substitute this category contains personal pronouns such as (he, she, it... etc.) and demonstratives such as (this, that, these, those) plus the verb do.
2. Proper name always refers to the names of people, places, animals, spirits, and vehicles. It cannot be rendered because it is a label, for example (Jack) must be Jack and cannot be rendered.
3. Abbreviation is the use of a segment of words for a whole. It is the substituting of long words or expressions with their first letter or morpheme for example the word UNICEF refers to United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund and the word (phone) for telephone.
4. English phrasal compound: a noun or a verb or an adjective that consists of two or more simple words and often is hyphenated (-) such as (boy-friend). They can be further subdivided into:

- A. Compound nouns can be formed by:
1. Verb –noun (VN) such as (swearword), (drop hammer), (playtime).
 2. Noun-noun (NN) such as (hairnet), (butterfly net)
 3. Adjective-noun (AN) such as (blackboard), and (greenstone).
 4. Preposition-noun (PN) such as (in-group), (outpost).
- B. Compound adjectives (CA) can be classified into three categories:
1. Noun-Adjective (NA) such as (sky-high), (coal –black). (Oil-rich).
 2. Adjective –adjective (AA) (grey-green), (red-hot).
 3. Preposition-adjective (PA) such as (under full), (overactive).
5. Phrasal nouns which is the final category comprise compound verbs, which consist of a simple verb and one or more particles. They are so named because they resemble phrases rather than independent words, but perform the functions of single words. They can also be further subdivided into:
- A. Verb +adverbial particle as in (get in).
 - B. Verb +preposition as in (come across).
 - C. Verb +adverbial particle +preposition as in (run out of).
 - D. Verb +object +adverbial particle such as (bring a child up)
 - E. Verb +adverbial particle +object bring up a child.
6. Figures of speech are categorized as idioms. They include:
- A. A simile includes two different things that are compared to clarify sameness in one thing. It is done by the words like (as, like) for example (as easy as cake) and (he is tall like his father).
 - B. The metaphor looks like a simile in that it compares two things without as or like for example (she is my home)
 - C. Personification it is the style by which the inanimate thing is dealt as animate for example (walls have ears) the inanimate wall can hear.
 - D. Hyperbole in this figure of speech we use exaggeration to get more effect of the statement such as (I love you for a thousand years) no one can live for a thousand years which means that love for the entire life.
7. Slang may be defined as the use of informal language by a group of particular people. it is treated as idioms and often uses metaphors and ellipses. It includes five categories as below:
- A. Fresh and Creative refers to creating a new informal type of vocabulary for example the word (bae) which means a term of endearment used for the romantic couple.
 - B. Flippant is compounded by two words or more like (a piece of cake) which means very easily, it does not correlate with the denotative meaning.
 - C. Imitative is derived from Standard English for example (aint) for the idiom (I am not).
 - D. The acronym is a slang word composed of the first letters of words for example (ROTFL) is the acronym for (roll on the floor laughing)
 - E. Clipping is classified as a type of slang idiom; it is created by omitting portions of a word to shorten it while maintaining its meaning; for instance, "examination" could be rendered as "exam."
 - F. Moon (1998, p: 22) pointed out that idioms are a subclass of metaphor, and he divided idioms into four categories:
 1. Transparent idioms are very close to literal meaning like, (*see the light*).
 2. Semi-transparent idioms contain metaphorical sense, for example (*break the ice*).
 3. Semi-opaque idioms have figurative meaning part and literal meanings such as (*know the rope*) which means: (do the job).
 4. Opaque idioms are regarded as the most challenging category because their meanings cannot be deduced from their constituent parts. For instance, "*spill the beans*" signifies "disclose the secret."

4. Restrictions of Idioms

In her book (1992:63) Baker identified some syntactic and grammatical restrictions that a writer/speaker should avoid in translating idioms to evade any potential changes in the meaning of idioms, they are:

1. Addition the meaning of an idiom is changed by adding any word to the idiom for example the idiom (red herring) does not afford any addition like very red herring because it is no longer an idiom.
2. Deletion/ no bit of an idiom could be deleted to do so would alter the meaning of the idiom for example the idiom (spill the beans) would be turned into an ordinary sentence if we omit the word (the) from the idiom.
3. Substitution/ no word, even if they are synonyms, can be substituted for another. For instance, the idiom "the long and short of it" refers to the fundamental facts of a situation; therefore, the adjective "long" cannot be substituted for its synonym "tall," despite their similar or equivalent meanings.

4. Modification/ no grammatical structure of an idiom could be altered for it leads to the destruction of the idiom meaning for example the idiom (lock stock and barrel) is no longer an idiom if we changed the structure into (stock and barrel lock)
5. Comparison/ the idiom (be in hot water) which means be in trouble does not afford the comparative form of the adjective (hot) for it alters the idiom.
6. Passivization/ of the idiom (kick the bucket) does not afford to transform into passive so we cannot say (the bucket was kicked) for it would be turned into an ordinary sentence and no longer regarded as an idiom.

5. Features of Idioms

Bell (1974:3) identified certain common features that assist in recognizing the idiom below are some characteristics.

1. Alteration of grammatical rules
Not always idioms are grammatical, but they are accepted and established by the users of language with fixed meaning and structure for example the idiom (it is ages since we met) there is no concord between the singular and plural.
2. Conventional phrase
Idioms are fixed expressions that are agreed upon and known nearly by all member societies for example (How are you doing) is an idiom used to ask about health. (Once in a blue moon) which means very rare.
3. Alteration of word order
Idioms often deviate from the English word order for example (It may be well ahead of time) normal word order (It may well be ahead of time) (Probably) idiom.
4. Figurativeness
The main feature of the idiom is that words are used metaphorically for example the idiom (to bury the hatchet) is an opaque idiom which means to be friends after a disagreement

6. Difficulties in Translating Idioms

1. Baker (1992:68) presented the principal difficulties that translators may encounter in translating:
The receptor language may not have an equivalent idiom. The method by which a language chooses to clarify or not clarify multiple meanings cannot be predicted and only occasionally aligns with the method chosen by another language to convey a similar meaning. A language can convey a specific meaning through the use of a set phrase, idiom, or individual word. Idioms, such as "your faithfully," can be specific to a particular culture, like English. However, they may not have an equivalent in the Arabic language.
2. "An idiom or fixed expression may have a similar counterpart in the target language, but its context of use may be different, the two expressions may have different connotations, for instance, or they may not be pragmatically transferable"
3. The practice of incorporating idioms into written communication, including the appropriate context and frequency of usage, may vary between the source language and the target language.
Mona Baker recognizes two areas which are the capability to render idiom and recognize it correctly. She reports two cases that may result in translating an idiom.
 1. When the literal meaning of idiom makes sense too.
 2. When there is an idiom in the target language that shares a similar structure but has a different meaning.
Newmark (1988:28) asserted that when translating idiomatic expressions, it is particularly challenging to achieve both semantic equivalence and frequency equivalence. The primary difficulty in translating idioms lies not in grammar but in lexical aspects such as words, collocations, and fixed phrases or idioms.

Davies (2004:193) outlined numerous challenges that translators may face when translating idioms, including:

1. Identification of idiomatic expressions.
2. Lack of a corresponding term in the target language.
3. A corresponding equivalent in the receptor language with a distinct usage context.
4. An idiom in the source language has both a literal and idiomatic meaning that are identical.
5. Conventions are different in context and frequency of use.

7. Strategies of Translating Idioms

Baker (1992:75) reported four strategies for translating idioms as below:

1. Using an Idiom of Similar Meaning and Form

This strategy incorporates idioms in the target language and conveys the same meaning as the idioms in the source language and the target language has the same structure. This matching occurs when the source language and the target language belong to the same language family and share cultural similarities. Here is an illustration of how to employ this approach:

1. "A true friend does not stab in the back. (ST)
2. "لا يطعن الصديق الحقيقي في الظهر". (TT)

It is regarded as the ideal strategy for translating idioms.

2. Using Idioms of Similar Meaning but Dissimilar Form.

This strategy involves the use of an idiom or fixed expression in the target language that carries the same meaning as the idiom in the source language, but with different words. Finding an equivalent idiom in the target language that conveys the same meaning as the idioms in the source language can be challenging. When translating idiomatic expressions, the translator must possess a strong cultural foundation to accurately determine the intended meaning and identify an appropriate equivalent idiom that serves the same purpose in the target language. Here is an example that illustrates the application of this strategy in idiom translation:

1. "How nice to remember your play days!" (ST).
2. "ما أجمل ان تتذكر ايام الرغد والرخاء!" (TT).

3. Translation by paraphrase.

This is a renowned method for translating idioms when the translator is unable to locate an equivalent in the target language. Through the implementation of this approach, the translator diminishes the significance of an idiom by employing a solitary term or a collection of terms that correspond to the idiom's meaning. Indeed, the translator can employ this approach for idioms that exhibit a lower degree of cultural specificity compared to others. Here is an illustration of how to employ this approach when translating idioms:

1. Wrong end of the stick (ST)
2. (اخطأ في فهم) (TT).

4. Translation by Omission

There are situations where the translation must exclude the idiomatic expression because it has a similar idiom in the language being translated to, or when the translator is unable to rephrase the meaning of the idiom. Baker (1992, p.77) states that omission is permissible in certain cases, specifically when there is no comparable term in the target language. Furthermore, in cases where paraphrasing proves challenging, an idiom may ultimately be excluded for stylistic purposes.

1. "If it is all the same to you, I'd rather take my chance in open space" (ST)
2. "افضل استخدامه في الفضاء" (TT)

In his work, Helleklev (2006:27) outlined four strategies for managing idioms. Contrary to numerous scholars, he suggests employing a literal translation approach for idioms.

1. By rendering an idiom into a synonymous idiom.
2. Proceeding in a manner where each word is considered individually and sequentially.
3. Using a commonly used phrase to explain.
4. An ordinary phrase is rendered by employing an idiom.

8. Data Collection Steps

Twenty-five idioms were collected from twenty-five movies in their contexts of four types of idioms identified by Moon (1998) from YouTube channels as data for analysis. The data includes six transparent idioms, six semi-transparent idioms, six semi-opaque idioms, and seven opaque idioms to cover all types of idioms for the study. All the idioms are in English, then they have been translated from English into Arabic. The data of this study has been collected in the following steps:

1. Twenty-five idioms have been collected from YouTube channels of all types of idioms (see Appendix 1).
2. Ten M.A students were chosen purposively by the researcher from the University of Tikrit, College of Arts, and Translation Department.
3. The researcher has met the students and explained the aims of the study, asked them to take part in the study to fulfill the study objectives, among the twenty-eight M.A students only ten have agreed to participate in the study.
4. The researcher gave the idioms with their contexts and asked them to translate the idioms by a link over two days.
5. The researcher has clarified the strategies adopted for translation to the students and the model of translation during the meeting.
6. Finally, the translations have been collected to be ready for analysis.

9. Test of the Study

After collecting data from movies concerning types of idioms, the idioms were asked to be rendered by ten M.A. students to discover the principal difficulties the students face in rendering the given idioms of the study. The questionnaire includes 25 idioms which were chosen from movies in their contexts including the four types of idioms. The proposed translations by the students were analyzed linguistically according to the linguistic model proposed by Moon (1998:4) to

classify idioms. The idioms then were classified into four types: first transparent idioms whose their meaning is nearly equal to the literal meaning of the idiom , second the semi-transparent idioms which has metaphorical meaning , third the semi-opaque idioms whose meaning is unrelated sense to their components, one part is literal and the other is figurative, the last kind is the opaque idioms, they are the most difficult one for they are not compositional and not easy to be understood because they are pragmatically constructed.

10. The Model of Translation

The model of translation adopted by the researcher is the one proposed by Newmark (1981:39). In this model, Newmark presents the semantic method of translation which relies on the transmitter's cognitive processes as an individual and helps the target language reader with connotations if they are a crucial part of the message.

The second method is communicative by which the target language reader focuses on a specific language and culture. Semantic translation sticks to the source language culture, while communicative translation moves foreign components into the target language culture. Whenever the two cultures are different, the task of translation will be harder. Semantic translation is not restricted by age and local area and it is done with every generation without limitation. While communicative translation is ephemeral and restricted in its contemporary context. Semantic translation often tilts to source text and loss of meaning. Communicative translation could sometimes be smarter than the source text in force and clarity though it loses the content of meaning.

After that comes the four strategies suggested by Mona Baker (1992:72) in rendering idioms. They include using an idiom similar in meaning and form the translator tries to find an idiom in the target language which is equivalent both in meaning and form which is the first strategy. The second strategy includes using an idiom in the target language similar in meaning but has different form. The third strategies is paraphrasing this strategy is widely used by translators. It is used when the translator cannot find the equivalent idiom is not found in the target language. The fourth strategy is translating by omission it is used when leaving an idiom untranslated is not harmful.

11. Data Analysis Procedures

The researcher has followed the following steps in analyzing each source text:

1. Analyzing and classifying twenty- five idioms.
2. Presenting the Arabic text.
3. Explaining the text based on the model of translation.
4. Presenting ten translations for ten students who agreed to take part in translating.
5. Translations have been sorted into appropriate and inappropriate in a table for each idiom.
6. Identifying the adopted strategy by the translator.
7. Comparing the translation of the students with the suggested translation.
8. Identifying the adopted model of translation into communicative translation and semantic translation.
9. Presenting the suggested translation.

The analysis of data begins with choosing 25 idioms from movies including four types of idioms as a source language with their translations, then the researcher proposed translation-making analysis to the source language idioms to sort them as transparent, semi-transparent, semi-opaque and opaque, according to Moon (1998:4) as a first step. Secondly, the study classifies the translations according to Newmark (1981:39) as communicative or semantic method. Baker's (1992) taxonomy was used to identify the translation strategies utilized by students which are using idioms similar in meaning and form, using idioms similar in meaning with different forms, paraphrasing, and finally translation by omission. Then the researcher gives his opinion if the translations are appropriate or inappropriate in comparing to the standard translations. Then a table was made to show the percentages of idiom types of the target language. The tables were organized according to the methods of translation, the strategies, and the percentage of appropriateness.

12. Analysis and Discussion

The analysis implies the type of idiom and the translations of students and sorting them according to Newmark's model of translation, then grouping them into appropriate and inappropriate. After that, the analysis identified the adopted strategy according to Baker (1992), and then a comparison with the suggested translation was introduced.

13. Opaque idioms

The first seven idioms are opaque as below:

Idiom 1	The name of the film	The suggested translation
1- Why don't you tell me that you had a crush on Pan? Well, <i>let the cat out of the bag.</i>	The Office 2006	انكشف السر

The source language idiom type is opaque according to (Moon: 1998) because the meaning of the idiom does not equal its components. When the idiom is in the context, it was translated by the students using the following translations:

SL	TL
<i>Let the cat out of the bag</i>	انكشف السر خرج القط افشى السر الامور خارج السيطرة القط خارج الحقيبة خارج متداول اليد القطه خارج الحقيبة انكشف السر خارج النص خرج الامر عن السيطرة

Appropriate translations	Inappropriate translation
(1,3,8,)	2,4,5,6,7,9,10,

According to (Moon: 1998) the idiom (*let the cat out of the bag*) is regarded as an opaque idiom because the meaning of its components is not equal to its literal meaning. Only the translations (1, 3, and 8) with (30%) percentage are successful as the students used a suitable strategy which is the translation by using different forms but the same meaning, and the right method is communicative translation. The other seven translations (2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10) with a percentage of (70%) failed to succeed in achieving suitable translation as the students used semantic translation and inappropriate strategies.

The suggested translation is (انكشف السر), students' numbers (1, 3, and 8) used different forms but the same meaning strategy. Students' numbers (2, 5, and 7) applied similar forms and meaning strategies. The paraphrasing strategy was used in translation numbers (4, 6, 9, and 10).

4.1 Conclusions

The conclusions of this study can be summed up in the following points:

1. The results of the analysis showed that M.A. students faced many challenges when translating idiomatic expressions from English into Arabic such as a lack of awareness of the cultural differences between English and Arabic. It is obvious from the subject 'translation that a lack of understanding of the source language's cultural patterns, unawareness of the cultural differences, misusing the appropriate technique and the tendency to use literal translation that is not successful in most cases, using paraphrasing technique rather than introducing the target language equivalent and the unfamiliarity with idiomatic expressions are main causes for the failure in translating such expressions. This result verifies the first hypothesis sets for this study.
2. Almost all the researchers agree that familiarizing students with their own culture, foreign culture, and English cultural patterns (traditions habits customs ceremonies entertainment, and social background), reading more books, newspapers, and magazines; in addition to watching English series and films. Further, source language idiomatic expressions in textbooks, conversations, and dialogues are required. In addition, it is important to find a target language idiom rather than translating such an idiom by paraphrasing. As well as, being familiar with the adopted strategies may help students' abilities to translate more properly. This conclusion corresponds with hypotheses numbers two and three.
3. The analysis displays that the type of idiom has a minor impact on understanding its meaning and aiding an appropriate translation.

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